

STRUCTURE AND COMPONENTS OF GENDER CULTURE DEVELOPMENT IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. Women's education is critical to the country's entire development. It's similar to an effective medicine that may know how to cure a patient and recover their health. A well-educated lady is capable of managing both her personal and professional lives. The physical and intellectual growth of the child is the moral goal of education. Education's true objective is to provide students with "full knowledge" or "greater information".

Keywords: pedagogical education; gender culture; higher education; gender equality; international law; women; women rights protection; leadership.

Definition of gender and basic concepts. The relevance of the research topic is caused by the peculiarity of the modern development of society in general and Russian in particular, which is associated with the processes of globalization, informatization, individualization, which caused crises in various spheres of life, including the crisis in the management of organizations. Organizations (formal and informal) are affected by the ongoing crisis changes in society. Designed to coordinate people's activities, they lose: firstly, their functions related to achieving goals and results that a person cannot achieve alone; secondly, its orderliness, coordination, smoothness of social relationships; social positions (statuses), roles; thirdly, manageability and communication system.

The basis of any HR organization is not people in general, but men and women who perform their professional and status roles in the organization. Each of them strives to achieve the desired status, success in their chosen activity, make a career, get recognition from others. But tender asymmetry in all spheres of activity leaves an imprint on these processes.

In order to define the term "gender" and understand how it differs from gender, it is necessary to consider both of these terms. Gender refers to the universal biological differences between women and men. Only minor differences in roles can be attributed to biological ones. For example, only women can bear children.

Gender equality is an equal assessment by society of the similarities and differences between women and men. This is the possession of equal status by women and men through equal conditions for the realization of human rights and potentials.

The living conditions of women and men differ significantly from each other, to a certain extent due to the reproductive function of women. However, they should not negatively affect the living conditions of women and men, lead to discrimination, but, on the contrary, be taken into account accordingly, which should be expressed in an equal distribution economic, social and political opportunities.

Discrimination is the diminution, violation (actual and/or legal) of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of a person and citizen based on their nationality, religion, gender, race, language, origin, property and official status, place of residence, membership in public associations or any social groups. In the field of international relations, discrimination is the granting of lesser rights to citizens and organizations of a State and privileges than citizens and organizations of other states.

Gender discrimination is gender-based discrimination, a practice by which one gender is given preference over another. In patriarchal societies, women are subject to gender discrimination in such areas as employment, wage differentiation, political and religious careers, housing, social policy, the right to property in civil and criminal law, sexual harassment at work and domestic violence.

Higher education through "gender glasses".

The traditional view of the world and the order of things is undergoing serious transformations today due to various processes taking place in the economy, politics, social sphere, culture. One of these changes is the appearance of the principle of gender equality on the agenda of various political parties, public organizations and educational institutions.

For example, in the picture of the world of modern man, self-development and self-realization have long been strengthened as the fundamental components of happiness. Gender equality can be called the behavioral model of people in society when a person's self -development and self-realization do not depend on social expectations attributed to his gender.

Everyone understands the meaning of the expression "to look at the world through rose-colored glasses", which cannot be said about the expression "gender glasses". And if in the case of pink glasses it is clear that a person embellishes reality, then in the case of gender glasses, the question arises, and what do we see when we put on these very glasses. Let's try them on and try to look through gender glasses at our education.

Education, or rather, the educational model of modernity, remains traditional, namely the gender role. Gender role model²¹ is based on specific (stereotypical) ideas about what functions a man and a woman perform in society. The same model works in Belarus, which means that our education and upbringing translates stereotypical ideas, in many respects, I must say, outdated, about the social purpose of men and women.

For example, a man is represented as a defender, a breadwinner, a politician, a businessman, strong, brave, active. A woman most often appears in the image of a mother, a keeper of the hearth, a counselor, weak, passive.

The picture of the world of modern society is unisex in clothes, shoes, hairstyles. This, despite everything, is the absence of barriers among young people between typically male and female occupations and professions. This is a male householder and a woman in the role of head of government. These are Formula 1

drivers and Nobel laureates of both sexes. This, along with the traditional family, is a variety of forms of partnership and cohabitation.

The educational model, which focuses on gender equality, is also changing. In a gender-oriented model, it is important to realize that, that many stereotypes were formed millennia ago and are supported by culture. But, along with all this, there is something new, something that spreads through contemporary art and subcultures. And this new thing also strongly influences our picture of the world, as well as traditional values. As a result, the question arises about the need to develop new, gender-based technologies of upbringing and education.

Including the use of the latest achievements of Information Technology in education, their orientation to education and training, the efforts of the women scientists of our country are growing significantly. It is known to all of us that in the system of public education, secondary special and professional education, higher education, classes are also conducted using internet technologies and computer tools, and quality is much more effective. Because the full involvement of educators in the course process through traditional teaching methods is now a much more complex task. It is necessary to create an unconventional lesson environment in order to attract all the attention of the audience to the lesson. In this case, the use of VR (virtual reality-virtual reality) technologies will give a particularly great effect. Students, seeing, hearing and writing in the course process, absorb the information they learn in 3D format, feeling that environment, like a participant in the process. That I, today there are different type of computer.

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